

THE CHARACTER OF TUKLIBOY KUCHKAROV IN THE NOVEL “OLABUJI”

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Abstract. *People's writer of Uzbekistan Shukur Kholmirezayev is distinguished by his creativity, fearlessly penning life events in his time. This article reflects on the events of the pre-independence period through the character of Toqliboy Kochkarov in the novel "Olaboji" by the writer.*

Keywords: *artistry, writing skills, portraiture, image tools, the idea of the work, the spiritual world of the hero, individual style, artistic work, image term, artistic image and man, generalization, individualization, artistic texture, aesthetic impact, imagination and mind participation.*

Finding a way to the hearts of the people requires great skill from the writer. We can confidently say that Shukur Kholmirezayev, whom we are conducting research on, is a writer who has found a way to the people's hearts with his tireless research and discovery of something new in each of his works. We can prove this point on the example of his novel “Olaboji”.

In this novel, Shukur Kholmirezayev shed light on life events and conflicts and expressed his reaction to them. He put big and big problems in the scenes of small life pictures. He finds the subtlest aspects of the incidents and events selected from life, finds characteristic points, describes them in detail, and through this makes a deep artistic analysis of the relationship between a person and society, between people. It fully describes a person, the experiences of the heroes, the conflicts between them, and spiritual values. As the first factor that ensures the artistry of the work, the author writes about the materials he is interested in and familiar to him.

Since artistry is both the soul and the soul of art, one of the main means of creating it is the artistic image, and it is considered the central problem of the science of literary studies.

Because in the science of literary studies, “image” means not only the events perceived in the human mind, but also the life realized, reworked (interwoven) and depicted by the artist through the medium of words. “... There is nothing random or superfluous in it. All parts are subordinate to the whole, all are directed towards one goal, all together bring forth one beauty, integrity, individuality” [2, 101].

Art's thinking through images is its specific, i.e. defining characteristic as a species. An artist perceives the world by means of an artistic image, expresses the essence he perceives and his emotional attitude to what he perceives. In this sense, the image is considered a form of thinking, a method of literature and art; The way of thinking typical of literature and art is called "figurative thinking" because it thinks through images.

As the writer himself said, the characters of each of his works, whether they are positive or negative, try to approach him as much as possible in a positive and negative way. After all, our people say that “God is blameless”. Therefore, every person has good and bad qualities. We cannot admit this ourselves. Many writers ignore this and try to portray positive characters and negative characters with negative characters. This has a negative effect on the value of the work. We notice

that Shukur Kholmirzaev paid great attention to this situation in his works. In particular, the above-mentioned leaders in the novel “Olaboji” have similar situations.

“The task of the novel is not to raise issues, but life itself to absorb cross-cutting issues into human destiny”, it is to show the dramas hidden under these issues, to show them through artistically perfect images. Therefore, everything in a work of art, including the importance of the raised issue, depends on the perfection of the artistic image, that is, the ability of the writer to create a “living person” capable of shaking the reader [3, 116-117]. The ability to create a “living person” in turn depends on how well one can use psychological analysis, the ability to integrate it into the texture and problem of the work [7, 56].

The writer was able to create such “living people” in the work. As we mentioned at the beginning of our work, the characters of Ulton and Tukliboy Kuchkarov are at the heart of the novel.

One is an ordinary teacher, Ulton, and the other is Tukliboy Kuchkarov, the head of the district party. These two are very different from each other.

At the beginning of the work, Tukliboy Kuchkarov leaves a different impression on us. He always laughs and talks, cheerful, cheerful, mature, careful, thoughtful, alert, kind, poetic person.

“Nowadays, we have to hear a lot that education is lagging and the level of students is low. Isn't that right, Comrade Zakir Orinovich?”

“That's right, Comrade Kochkarov” he said.

- Thank you, but it is interesting that when Ulton and Baharoy were studying, we heard the same things a lot. Isn't that so?

“So, so” said Ugok Tolaganov.

- I mean; we are always thirsty for life! Our demand is increasing day by day, which is good in one way! Giving in to complacency, thinking that this is life, is a sign of stopping...” [9, 118].

True, all the positive qualities we mentioned above do not raise Tukliboy Kuchkarov to the level of a positive hero in the literal sense of the word. But because of these qualities and negative qualities, he acquires the character of a living person. In illuminating the character of Tukliboy Kuchkarov, Adib tries to reveal his mental image by describing his actions.

In the play, there are three characters who collide with each other from the beginning to the end of the plot, and the inner secrets of their activities are analyzed. All the characters in the novel have relationships with Ulton. For this reason, we have an excursion into the psyche of each character, the psychology of the people who made them like this, who works only for their own benefit and stops at nothing. The writer was able to give these situations in the character of Tukliboy Kuchkarov. The following words of Tukliboy Kuchkarov to Ulton confirm our opinion: “The district party committee is the owner of the district! He calls the person he wants, his staff, and orders him to do what he wants...” [9, 30]. It is clear from this passage that vices such as disregard for human dignity are embedded in his soul. Of course, he was not a self-centered person. In the background of events, we feel the power of the environment to influence a person. This becomes clear during the reading of the work, in some cases it surpasses the psychology of the individual and the psychology of the society. Of course, this happens against the background of Kuchkarov's character. He tries to claim all the achievements in the region as his own. His supporters also support his work. If they don't support him, he will send Ulton to the insane asylum because he was caught cheating with his wife on the bank with his five children, and sent to

shepherds with his five children because he couldn't get along with him. can be set to "ji". As a result, there is not a single person who thinks more broadly than him in the entire district. A tool that helps to fully imagine his character - Ulton, through the image of the spiritual world of springs, the character traits of this character are revealed more widely, which is manifested in the form of specific manifestations of the writer's psychologist. At the beginning of the work, he reveals his unique features and actions through the image of Ulton's spiritual world in dark colors. If the writer didn't have to reveal Ulton and his adventure in the picture, the characteristic aspect of that time embodied in Kuchkarov would not have been revealed, and we would have continued to convince ourselves that life is going smoothly. "The spiritual world of each character is closely connected with his personal life" [7, 86]. The same situation is observed in the work. Kuchkarov's personal life collides with the life of society. This is related to its negative or positive impact on the development of society. Therefore, the psychological analysis related to this image becomes a spiritual mirror of his personal life and the period in which he lives. So, psychological analysis has been able to rise to the level that connects the individual and the society.

Tukliboy Kuchkarov, who initially made an impression on us as a person of positive qualities, appears before our eyes with his negative qualities that outweigh the positive qualities during the reading of the novel. He leaves an impression on us as a person who cares about his reputation and will stop at nothing. He traps Bahor, who is the same age as his child, and so that this secret will not be revealed to others, he takes the girl to him as a "kindness" to his student Ulton. He goes to fortune-telling himself. It makes a good impression on people. This can also be seen in the following passage:

“Think for yourself: if Tukliboy Kuchkarov, who does not go to the wedding of the directors of the state farm, will stand at the head of the shepherd's campaign!”

Yes, may the soul of Tukliboy Kuchkarov be healthy. “Civilization will be the same” said Zakir Orinov [9, 73].

This thing is deeply ingrained in the psyche of Tukliboy Kuchkarov, who works for his own benefit, that he does not even suffer from this work, nor does he suffer from mental anguish. Satisfied with this work, he makes their weddings “excellent”, “beautiful”, “exemplary” together with his people. By doing these things, he will save his reputation and position and avoid scandalous scandals. Erk gets rid of Ulton, who fights for independence and gives his life for nature.

This man, who used to work as a literature teacher, likes to read from Mashrab's ghazals every two sentences and give examples from them:

“Mashraba, serve your neighbor with all your heart and soul,

This period is also a booty, I wish it would not be taken” [8, 31].

On the surface, this man appears to be a master propagandist interested in our classic literature, but in reality he uses values to mask his dark deeds. It is true that memorizing the ghazals of representatives of classical literature and analyzing them in full is a difficult task. For this reason, we can positively evaluate his work, and we can even respectfully mention that he has a high devotion to poetry, is able to use his pen, and devote time to this work diligently while working as the head of the head of major. Also, the following words he said in a conversation with Ulton about national heroes at the end of the work will not fail to make any person shiver:

“Yes, great guys have died” he said. - My grateful father used to say: “Today's young men are getting smaller”. Sadness, drinking, smoking... is ruining me right now. Their souls were free; they were free birds!

Pan-Turkists passed in the twenties?... I'm with you, he said in a bitter whisper.- Their movement was actually a very progressive movement" [11, 106-107]. Or we can see that the writer sheds light on his psyche by giving short portraits of him throughout the work:

“At that time, Tukliboy Kuchkarov - a cheerful, cheerful person who recites a couplet from classical poets in every two sentences - was not only the director of the boarding school, but also studied language and literature at the school of Ulton”[8, 23].

Above, we get acquainted with the portrait of Tukliboy Kuchkarov through Ulton's eyes. Below we also observe this portrait image through Ulton's eyes:

“Astana crossed the threshold and fed it into the net. And he saw Tukliboy Kuchkarov, smiling and staring at the head of the long table, ... dressed in a blue suit, wearing a red necktie, and ... his former teacher, who had become much fuller, and his face had become rounder than usual[8, 23]. We did not bring his portrait here for nothing. After all, a portrait is one of the factors that reveal the spiritual world of a person. During the reading of the work, we see that the writer increased the psychological “burden” on him by describing short portraits of Tukliboy Kuchkarov and other heroes.

Kuchkarov's way of life is to manage the power and to pass judgment when necessary. According to him, "The district party committee is the owner of the district. He calls the person he wants, the personnel he wants, and orders him to do what he wants”. Kuchkharov always adheres to these words, which are embedded in his spiritual world. One thing prevails in his mind - to live well in the world and get by. He is a cunning person who will stop at anything for his reputation and benefit. He does everything very carefully. Ulton has a purpose even when he corrects Spring, that is, when he sends them to check their school work. The next day, he calls them to the district, enters the role based on a pre-planned plan and fulfills his role admirably.

One can come to such a conclusion after getting acquainted with Tukliboy Kuchkarov's work. By introducing this person and giving events, the writer shows that there are still such people in life, unfortunately, such leaders have decided many destinies in the recent past, hurt people's hearts, damaged material and cultural wealth, and are not in the society. to give the image of a person facing a spiritual crisis aimed at and was able to achieve.

In general, Shukur Kholmiraev does not blindly follow the belief that a positive character has a positive image, and a negative character should be presented in a negative way. That is why the attitude towards his works and heroes has not changed today. He treats each of his heroes with his own love and respect. This is also evident in the description of his appearance and mentality. In order to clearly show the nature of this hero, he uses landscapes alternately. He pays special attention not only to landscapes, but also to the construction of monologues and dialogues. That is why the image and mentality of the heroes have a special place in his works.

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